

Long Term Satellite Propulsion System

At present satellite have a life span of 8 to 9 years maximum. With long term satellite propulsion system the ion fuel is recycled inside the satellite and the satellite can have a infinite life theoretically as it is only fueled by solar and gravity field combined. The project is classified under Systematic Invention Unit.

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The physical environment system will influence during their development and formation. This stage will develop information regarding their generation stage under mechanical stress and physical space constraints within the...

